

**ВПЛИВ ПЕДАГОГІЧНОГО ВИХОВАННЯ НА РОЗВИТОК ОСОБИСТОСТІ СЕРЕД
СТУДЕНТІВ-МЕДИКІВ**

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**THE IMPACT OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION ON PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT AMONG
MEDICAL STUDENTS**

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Анотація

У статті проведено оцінку впливу педагогічного виховання на формування особистості студента-медика. Педагогічна теорія є одним із критеріїв формування особистості особливо в період дистанційного виховання у студентів медиків шляхом самореалізації, самовиховання, самооцінки, тощо, що і є актуальним у сьогоденні. Нашою метою стало провести аналіз розвитку особистості, встановити роль педагогічної теорії у розвитку особистості студента-медика. В основу поставленої мети нами запропоновано 2 етапи методологічного обґрунтування в яких першим етапом є висвітлення особистості як поняття та її особливості; другий етап включав в себе розбір педагогічної теорії та її роль у вихованні студента медика. Обґрунтована вагома роль педагогічної теорії (виховання та майстерності) у формуванні особистості студента медика. З'ясовано, що протягом педагогічного виховання студент-медик здобуває освіту шляхом вивчення навчальних тем, внаслідок цього отримує як і особистісний розвиток, так і науковий. Під впливом педагогічного виховання виявлено всебічний розвиток, самовдосконалення, правильна самооцінка, самоосвіта, що так необхідно для реалізації поставленої мети та особистісного розвитку в суспільстві. Виявлено, що в період навчання студент - медик краще розуміє свою роль в суспільстві і у виборі навчання, що допомагає йому швидше та правильніше сформувати себе як «особистість». Правильний підхід викладача пришвидшує процес формування.

Abstract

The article evaluates the impact of pedagogical education on the formation of personality of a medical student. Pedagogical theory is one of the criteria for the formation of personality, especially in the period of remote education of students of physicians through self-realization, self-education, self-esteem, etc., which is relevant in the present. Our purpose was to analyze the development of personality, to establish the role of pedagogical theory in the development of personality of the student-medical. The basis of this goal we propose 2 stages of methodological justification in which the first stage is the coverage of personality as a concept and its peculiarities; The second stage included the analysis of pedagogical theory and its role in the raised student of the physician. The significant role of pedagogical theory (education and skill) in the formation of a student's personality is justified. It was found out that during pedagogical education the medical student receives education through the study of educational topics, as a result, both personal development and scientific. Under the influence of pedagogical education, comprehensive development, self-improvement, proper self-esteem, self-education, which is so necessary for the realization of the set goal and personal development in society were revealed. It is revealed that during the study period, a student - a doctor understands his role in society and in the choice of learning, which helps him to form himself as "personality" faster and more correctly. The correct approach of the teacher accelerates the formation process.

Ключові слова: педагогіка, теорія, особистість, студент, медик.

Keywords: pedagogy, theory, personality, student, physician.

The basis of personality development and formation is based on various personal factors (intelligence, responsibility, abstract, etc.) [1,4]. However, these factors are formed during communication, in the process of activity and self-development [13]. Pedagogical (educational) education has a significant impact on the formation of personality, which is based on developmental training and introspection [15,18].

Teaching methods are related to the purpose of learning, its content, the level of readiness of the subject for learning, the features of didactic tools, as well as the time determined to study the educational material. They are realized through a system of techniques and means of educational activity.

The emergence of innovative learning technologies is determined by the processes of globalization, integration and intensification [19].

In his property, I. Dichkivska evaluates innovative-pedagogical education as purposeful, systematic and consistent introduction into practice of original, innovative methods, techniques of pedagogical actions and means that cover a holistic educational process from determining its purpose to expected results [6].

However, since the twentieth century. A person-oriented learning process is only a learning system that allows you to create a model for selecting and evaluating the content of learning.

The first to put forward the ideas of developmental learning was Vygotsky L. Conclusion: "Any learning can be considered as developed, but not always developmental learning is personality-oriented" [14].

Modern studies of scientists are observing a positive tendency to combine various types of activity, the use of forms and tools that are interesting to students [17]. The study of different components of pedagogical theory can be interrelated, which can save significantly to organize time to organize game and learning activities and shorten the life of the desired result [2].

In Ukraine, this problem is addressed by many well-known scientists. In particular, V. Onishchenko repeatedly revealed the essence of pedagogy as a science and art in the work of pedagogical theories. In his articles, V. Onishchenko reveals pedagogical features during the present. "Fundamental pedagogical ideas in the affinity of categories and categorical structures of philosophical and pedagogical nosology are able to thematize and conceptualize such FPT, which will be able to facilitate the organization of the education-education-education-training of personally-oriented integration. These theories should reveal a multidimensional interaction between the subject of learning and the educational system, designed to ensure the formation of the subject (student, student, young person) of the necessary general cultural, spiritual-intelligent, moral-spiritual, spiritual-aesthetic, psychophysical, psychophysical, psychophysical, psychophysical, psycho-aesthetic, psycho-aesthetic, psycho-aesthetic, psycho-aesthetic psychological professional neoplasms. The set of such didactic cultural, spiritual and scientific-pedagogical ideas and images is a conceptual model of training of the future specialist and citizen of society"-wrote in his materials the author [11].

Equally skillfully and clearly covered his homes about pedagogy and personality OV Vozniuk. In his works, he revealed the problems of education (the system of harmonious development of man; organization of knowledge in the system of education: development of universal "matrices of knowledge"; psychological mechanism of decision-making and solving problems; professional development of the personality of the teacher; psychology of creativity and spirituality; aspects in pedagogy and psychology; postneoclassical paradigm of art education; problems of inclusive education; new paradigm of modeling and development of the historical and pedagogical process; etc.) [4].

V. Kremen also revealed the foundations of pedagogical theory [9].

The purpose of the article is to analyze the development of personality, to establish the role of pedagogical theory in the development of the personality of the student-medical.

Our task is to reveal all the features of pedagogical education and its impact on the development of personality.

Methodological justification. We have proposed several degrees of assessment of the impact of pedagogical education on the individual and on its formation.

The first stage of parsing the set tasks is the coverage of personality as a concept and its peculiarities. Consideration of the visuals of many scientists, both domestic and foreign, allowed us to form a model of modern personality, with which teachers meet daily. In the concept of "personality" of a medical student, the final is that she is a unique, individual and already formed, structured personality, who comes to learning to be aware, with his temperament, individual course of thoughts and a sense of life credo. Such a person has a choice for "inspired learning", or manifestation of "Ledar". Therefore, consideration of the concept of "personality" among medical students and the teacher is very relevant.

The second stage included the analysis of pedagogical theory and its role in the raised student of the physician. Pedagogical theory consisted of a combination of different methods of education and pedagogical skills of teachers. The assessment of pedagogical skills was evaluated by the approach of each teacher to presentation of the material, encouragement of a medical student to cognitive action. The component of which was methodological support (the use of visualities as a practical part, the use of schematic materials as a theoretical part). Methods of the teacher's interactive approach to the presentation of the material and encouragement for the analysis or comprehension of this educational material have been evaluated. As mentioned in the first stage, that the "personality" of each student is individual and temperamental, and the teacher's approach to the presentation of educational and scientific material is very relevant and personal. Since the student and the teacher have individual personal orientations, the approach of everyone in the study of educational material, understanding it and perception. Therefore, for the teacher it is the main to find the "golden mean"

of the student's perception in order to encourage him to study educational and scientific material.

Results and discussions. Nowadays, in scientific works, we find the concept of "personality". It is used in statements to students, students, etc. Despite gender and age, we always characterize the personality of each of us, taking into account the periods of development of the individual (childhood, youth, parental, mature). All these periods have a significant impact on personality development and outlook. However, few people also distinguish the student period, where each student only begins to comprehend their actions in practice and begins to adjust them in the future.

"Student" in Latin means "one who works honestly", "one who wants knowledge".

According to the definition of AS Vlasenko, "student body is a special social group, which is formed from different social entities of society and is characterized by special conditions of life, work, life, special social behavior and psychology, for which acquisition of knowledge and preparation of oneself for future work in social production, science and culture It is the main and mostly the only occupation." [3].

An important feature of students is that active interaction with different social formations of society, as well as the specificity of education in a higher education institution, create great opportunities for students to communicate. Therefore, a rather high intensity of communication is a specific feature of students. [7].

Psychologist Samarin Yu.A. highlights the contradictions inherent in student age:

- socio-psychological (between the development of the student's intellectual and physical forces and the strict limit of time and economic opportunities to meet increased needs);
- didactic (between the desire for independence in the selection of knowledge and rather rigid forms and methods of training a specialist of a certain profile);
- psychological and pedagogical (between a large number of information that comes with different channels, expands students' knowledge and lack of time, and sometimes the desire of mental processing, which leads to superficiality in knowledge and thinking and requires special work of teachers to deepen students' knowledge and skills) [9].

But each student should become a subject of his / her scientific (educational) activity, skillfully master this activity, master it, be capable of its implementation and creative transformation.

A significant contribution to a student's subjectivity is its role in life, the ability to communicate and self-consciousness. It allows the student to be a strategist of his or her activities, set and adjust their goals, realize motives, independently take actions and evaluate their adequacy, "build" life plans.

The term begins to enter into pedagogical research and pedagogical practice as determining the socially valuable quality of personality, which must be formed in the process of pedagogical interaction. The subjects of the pedagogical process are students and teachers.

Psychological and pedagogical analysis of the structure of the student's personality suggests about the

level of formation of his professional culture-the system of values, which forms his inner world and acts as a guide of behavior and formation of life and professional attitudes. [16].

Entering higher education institutions (institutions of the III-IV level of accreditation), each student has a partially, or fully formed person with a clear or partially, formed purpose (goals) and type of thinking.

Pedagogical theory includes a set of methods that are necessary for the further formation of a student's personality. One of the technologies of learning is an interactive method in which a parsing of educational material in small groups or pairs (cooperative training), playing the situation according to the plan of analysis of material (situational modeling), discussions or debate (development of discussion issues) and by type of "teaching" is used (collective-group learning) [14].

As you know, there are three stages of educational activity-the basic, the basic and the final.

The basic stage includes the use of norms and principles of morality (conversations in ethics, video tutorials of correct behavior, etc.). The main stage is familiarization with human and citizen rights (education, introspection, etc.) through reading works of art, ethical conversations, stories, exercises develop practical behavior skills in different activities. And the final stage - about the rights of the student, reading fiction, conversations about morality, etc. [8].

The combination of these stages enables the medical student to better understand the educational (scientific) material. These methods use visualization in the form of audio and video presentations, photographic materials and synchronous schematic reproduction of nosology. This example in medicine is video materials with stories about the patient's complaints, the history of the disease, pathogenetic data of the disease. The use of audio material in which the hearing perception of various auscultative pathologies, which will be differentiated from the norm, is also indistinguishable. This study of the material will better understand the pathology and evaluate its effect on the body-clinical course of mild, moderate or severe severity. Audio material always presents auscultative changes in five points of auscultation of the heart and the noise of pleural friction and possible pathological rales. This method is very relevant in the study of nosology in the period of distance learning, as it is a practical part of occupation, which helps to better understand auscultation in changes in various pathologies and norm. The use of systemic schematic methods in video materials will allow to better understand the pathogenetic links of the disease and their manifestation in laboratory and instrumental methods of examination of the patient and to predict possible complaints of the patient and changes in objective examination.

Proper presentation of the educational material to the medical student will allow him to form the correct conclusion (diagnosis). However, every student's psychology is different and the perception of the material will, of course, be different. As a result, it can be established that pedagogical education includes a psychological basis that can be a variety of mental phenomena

from the state of fear "before punishment for negligence and a formal attitude to learning to deep satisfaction and awareness of internal need for learning."

Having come to the universities, each student is an individual, with a formed personality. However, the pedagogical skills of teachers improve the personality of the medical student through education for etiquette, responsibility, self-realization, self-education, introspection. It is this period that is the main one, since it is at this time that the student-medical student independently experiences his difficulties among the new environment, adapts and becomes responsible for his actions.

It is known that modern domestic pedagogical theories are component in the development of students by assessing student psychology. In recent years, the moral and legal education of students, which shapes their hard work and morality, increase self-esteem, self-esteem, formation of norms for themselves and the ability to build a harmonious relationship with the environment.

Pedagogical theory is also considered as an area that examines the general patterns of education and means of solving pedagogical problems [12]; Studies the laws of transferring social experience to the older generations and active assimilation of this experience younger ("General Pedagogy"). It is believed that the subject of pedagogical theory is not only an analysis of scientific views on the essence, tasks, content and methods of education ("philosophy of education"), but also the practice of education, education and education itself [7].

Therefore, each teacher has its own approach to presenting the educational material and explaining it during the period of practical and seminars. In a medical university, the topic (pathology) is the first. It includes a survey of a medical student himself, his understanding of problems. Increased understanding of the material the teacher complements the photo with materials that presents the appearance of the patient himself (his skin manifestations-paint-skin (anemic syndrome), yellowness of the skin and sclera (cholestatic syndrome in hepatitis), etc.), his position (appearance "outside the petition" - Bechtereyev, "Ulna deviation" - rheumatoid arthritis, etc.), its state of severity (in the supine position - a serious condition of the course, in the sedentary and standing position - the average and mild state of the course), etc. But the main thing is the proper submission of the material by the teacher in order to attract the attention of the medical student and to interest him in the analysis of the educational material. In addition, the analysis of the material is well perceived and with a video, which clearly and concise changes of the above pathologies and their correct analysis in the pathogenesis of the disease are clearly and concisely presented. As practice shows, students not only enjoy this kind of analysis of medical topics, but also better remember the disassembled material. With the help of visualities, they are better oriented in diseases.

The use of the above interactive methods of submission of material will allow the student to "be as a

patient himself, to give correct explanations for complaints of the disease and to explain his condition correct", for the analysis of educational material.

Assessing the personality of the medical student, both subjectively and objectively, under the influence of pedagogical education, it was found that each student controls and corrects all the time. That is, the distribution of time in preparation for practical and seminars, personal time for self-development and self-improvement (favorite additional development (hobby) of a person, not related to learning; formation of behavior among classmates and classmates). This personality development allows every medical student.

In addition to the pedagogical educational process, the student-medical student receives education, through the study of educational topics, as a result, he receives both personal development and scientific. Therefore, during the study, the medical student receives the foundations of pedagogical theory - it is education, education, training, development, self-education (independent processing of educational material and performing independent work) and self-improvement (favorite additional development (hobby)).

Conclusions. The formation of the personality of the medical student depends directly on the pedagogical influence of the teacher (pedagogical theory). By pedagogical influence, a student is formed self-esteem, responsibility for obtaining education, which will allow to further self-realize and achieve the set goals in the medical sphere and not only. In addition, a medical student is a person who, through education, formation of ethical norms and, including self-realization, "creates" an individual with the ability to behave with dignity among classmates, classmates have become a society as a whole.

Given the individuality of each medical student and his psychological development, the influence of pedagogical education and learning is perceived differently. Therefore, each student requires a special individual approach to maximize the personality. The use in the practice of pedagogical theory of different features of teaching and taking into account the individual capabilities of a medical student does not always manage to form as much as possible the personality of medical direction, which is one of the issues of further research.

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